

PATHOPHYSIOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF NEPHRO- AND HEPATOTOXICITY DURING CHEMOTHERAPY AND THE ROLE OF AMINO ACID SUPPORT

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Chemotherapy of malignant neoplasms remains a key component in the treatment of oncological diseases, but is accompanied by a number of side effects, the most dangerous of which are toxic liver and kidney damage. These complications often limit the possibility of a full course of therapy, and in severe cases lead to the cancellation of treatment. Particularly pronounced organ toxicity is observed with the use of platinum series drugs (cisplatin , carboplatin), anthracyclines (doxorubicin), taxanes (paclitaxel , docetaxel), methotrexate and ifosfamide . Understanding the pathophysiological mechanisms of toxicity, as well as the search for ways to correct them, including through nutritional amino acid support, is an important area of clinical oncology.

Nephrotoxicity Cytostatics primarily result from direct damage to the tubular epithelium of nephrons, disruption of mitochondrial function, and induction of oxidative stress. Kidneys, with their high metabolic activity and dense system of transport proteins, are particularly sensitive to the accumulation of toxins and drug metabolites. Chemotherapy increases lipid peroxidation , damages membranes, disrupts reabsorption and secretion, causes interstitial inflammation, and in some cases, necrosis of the proximal tubules. Under conditions of reduced perfusion and oxygen deficiency, apoptosis mechanisms are also activated , leading to a progressive decrease in the filtration capacity of the kidneys.

Hepatotoxicity , in turn, is realized through several pathogenetic pathways: metabolic disorders in hepatocytes , mitochondrial damage, activation of inflammatory cascades and autoimmune processes. Many patients experience increased activity of liver enzymes (ALT, AST, GGT), cholestasis , fatty degeneration, drug-induced hepatitis. Mitochondrial dysfunction with ATP deficiency, impaired detoxification function, accumulation of ammonia and free radicals develop, which in turn affects the metabolism of other drugs and the patient's overall resistance to chemotherapy. Patients with underlying liver pathology - hepatozsis , hepatitis, cirrhosis - are especially vulnerable .

Given the complexity of pathogenesis and the involvement of multiple systemic links, it becomes obvious that isolated drug treatment is not always effective. Against the background of systemic inflammation and catabolism, it is

necessary to involve metabolic approaches, and here amino acids play a special role, capable of interfering with the regulation of oxidative stress, immune reactions, energy metabolism and tissue regeneration. Research in recent years confirms that certain amino acids can not only compensate for metabolic deficiencies, but also have an organ-specific protective effect.

Glutamine is the most studied amino acid in this context. As the main nitrogen donor, it is involved in the synthesis of nucleotides, amino acids and, most importantly, glutathione . Glutathione is a central component of the cellular antioxidant system, and its deficiency is accompanied by increased sensitivity of cells to toxic agents. Glutamine also maintains the integrity of the intestinal barrier, reduces the translocation of bacteria and endotoxins into the bloodstream, thereby preventing the development of a systemic inflammatory response.

Arginine, in addition to participating in protein synthesis, is a substrate for the formation of nitric oxide (NO), which plays an important role in the regulation of vascular tone, perfusion and immune response. With its deficiency, microcirculation is disrupted, the risk of tissue ischemia increases, and proapoptotic activity increases. Inclusion of arginine in nutritional support can reduce vascular spasms and restore local blood flow in the tissues of the liver and kidneys, thereby improving the conditions for reparation.

Glycine exhibits a pronounced anti-inflammatory and cytoprotective effect. It inhibits the activation of macrophages, reduces the production of proinflammatory cytokines and promotes the stabilization of cell membranes. In addition, glycine is involved in detoxification , facilitating the removal of toxic metabolites. In conditions of hepatotoxicity, it is able to inhibit the processes of fatty infiltration and oxidative damage to hepatocytes .

Taurine is an amino acid with osmoregulatory and membrane-stabilizing effects, especially effective in mitochondrial dysfunction. It stabilizes the inner mitochondrial membrane, preventing the release of cytochrome C and activation of apoptosis . In addition, taurine has antioxidant activity, protects hepatocytes from damage, normalizes bile formation and reduces the level of transaminases in toxic effects.

Major pathophysiological mechanisms of organ toxicity during chemotherapy and potential targets of amino acid support

Organ	Main mechanisms of damage	Target amino acids	Mechanism of protective action
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Liver	Oxidative stress, mitochondrial dysfunction, degeneration	stress, fatty	Glutamine , taurine	Antioxidant protection, mitochondrial stabilization
Kidneys	Tubular inflammation, apoptosis	injury,	Arginine, glycine	Improved microcirculation, anti-inflammatory effect
General	Systemic inflammation, catabolism		All of the above	Reduction of cytokine response, support of protein metabolism

Thus, amino acid support is a valid tool for metabolic correction aimed at reducing the severity of organ complications. Moreover, its use is consistent with the principles of multimodal therapy, combining pharmacological, nutritional and behavioral approaches. It is important to emphasize that this is not about replacing the main therapy, but about optimizing its tolerability, extending the possibilities of active treatment and reducing the risk of drug withdrawal due to toxicity.

From a practical point of view, amino acids can be administered either orally or parenterally, depending on the patient's condition, chemotherapy regimen, and the presence of concomitant pathologies. It is important to individualize the composition of the amino acid complex depending on the clinical situation. For example, in patients with predominant hepatotoxicity, the content of glutamine and taurine should be increased , and in case of nephrotoxicity , arginine and glycine. In some cases, it is possible to include additional nutrients - B vitamins, zinc, selenium - which participate in associated metabolic pathways.

In conclusion, it should be noted that amino acids are not just sources of protein, but active participants in metabolic and cellular processes that play a role in ensuring homeostasis. Their inclusion in the schemes of accompanying therapy of cancer patients receiving chemotherapy can reduce the risk of organ complications, increase the effectiveness of treatment, and improve the general condition of the patient. Further research in this area will optimize the dosage, duration and composition of nutritional support, making it a standard of oncological care on a large scale.

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